

Comparing the environmental impacts of dental amalgam with alternative restorative materials

Dental restorations are among the most common medical procedures performed globally,¹ with dental caries (tooth decay) being one of the major reasons for direct dental restorations.^{1,2} Historically, dental amalgam—a combination of liquid mercury and a powdered alloy of silver, tin, and copper—has been widely used for dental restorations.³ However, due to concerns over the potential risks of mercury to human health and the environment,^{3,4} the use of amalgam has continued to decline in the last 10 years.⁵ Other direct restorative materials (e.g. resin-based composite and glass ionomer) are now more frequently used, but their health and environmental impacts are not yet fully understood.

This systematic review was commissioned by the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) prior to the Conference of the Parties to the Minamata Convention on Mercury (COP-6).⁶ This review aimed to compare the health and environmental impacts of amalgam to other direct restoration materials, with findings intended to support and inform decisions on the future use of dental amalgam within the UK.

Key findings from 21 studies evaluating environmental impacts related to different direct restorative materials include:

- ◆ Fewer than half of the studies evaluating environmental impact measured a demonstrable effect, e.g. animal toxicity or carbon footprint. The majority only reported the *potential* for environmental impact, e.g. a level of toxicity associated with restorative materials, without indicating the degree to which this would cause harm.
- ◆ None of the studies were rated as low risk of bias, limiting trustworthiness of the findings.
- ◆ Most studies did not compare different restorative materials, i.e. included only one type of material, or included multiple materials without comparison.
- ◆ One lab-based study found that resin-based composites and glass-ionomer are less environmentally harmful than amalgam with respect to animal toxicity, but did not report using amalgam separators; where amalgam separators are used, mercury levels are significantly lower.

Full Project Report

Journal article:

[Briscoe, et al. Environmental impact of dental amalgam and alternative restorative materials: a systematic review. BDJ Open 12, 11 \(2026\)](#)

<https://enb.iisd.org/minamata-convention-mercury-cop6-summary>

**Minamata COP-6
Summary Report 3-7
November 2025**

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How did we do this review?

Research question: What are the **environmental** impacts of direct dental restorations made of amalgam compared to other direct restorative materials?

Finding evidence: We searched bibliographic databases with coverage of environmental science and dentistry. We conducted citation searches of relevant studies, and searched Google Search and the HealthcareLCA database.

Eligibility criteria: Studies reporting environmental impacts of materials used for direct dental restorations. Studies from high-income countries, published in English from 2007 onwards.

Synthesis: We initially grouped studies by type of restorative material evaluated, then by environmental impact examined. Broad impact categories include:

- Environmental impacts of mercury,
- Environmental impacts of monomers,
- Environmental impacts relating to multiple restoration materials.

Where reported, we extracted data on whether levels of toxic waste adhered to recommended levels in published guidance.

Overview of the evidence

Environmental impact evaluated	Studies, n
Mercury levels	
• Wastewater	5
• Solid waste	3
• Emissions	3
• Vapour	3
• Particulate matter	2
Monomer levels	
• Wastewater	2
• Particulate matter	1
• Emissions	1
Multiple materials	
• Carbon footprint	1
• Animal toxicity	2

21 studies reported environmental impacts or potential impacts.

Six studies included a **comparison** between different types of restorative material, including between amalgam, resin-based composites and glass-ionomer materials.

The remaining studies only assessed **one type** of relevant restorative material, or included multiple types of restorative materials without comparing them.

Most of the studies reported a measure of toxic waste (e.g. mercury levels in wastewater) without assessing its impact on the environment, e.g. animal toxicity or carbon footprint. These were classified as **potential environmental impact** versus **actual environmental impact** for studies which measured actual harm.

Study quality: Ten studies were rated as medium risk and 11 studies rated as high risk of bias.

Comparison of restorative materials

One lab-based study found that resin-based composite and glass-ionomer materials were less toxic to animals than amalgam. However, another study, set in a dental clinic where amalgam separators were used, found total suspended solids of glass-ionomer and resin-based composite were higher than amalgam, and were associated with animal toxicity.

Only one study measured the carbon footprint of restorative materials—but crucially only measured activity associated with undertaking fillings (e.g. travel), rather than the materials themselves.

Overall, few meaningful comparisons between different studies were possible due to study heterogeneity and limited data on actual harms.

What are the implications of this review?

This systematic review aimed to inform and support decision making around the future use of dental amalgam. Key implications include:

Policy makers:

- Findings from this review may be used in conjunction with other research and discussions from the Minamata COP-6 to support UK government policy regarding future use of amalgam.

Future research:

- Future studies should use either established guidance to assess whether levels of toxicity are compliant, or compare the effects of toxicity from different restorative materials on the environment.
- More evidence is required on how amalgam separators mitigate harms associated with amalgam whilst potentially have less effect on harms associated with alternative materials.
- More studies which measure carbon emissions are needed.

Clinical practice:

- The PPI group for this project indicated patients would like to be kept informed of the potential environmental implications of different restorative materials and involved in the decision-making process.
- Amalgam separators should be used to limit the extent of mercury entering the environment; however, these may be less effective for other materials.

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We are one of two research groups in the UK commissioned by the National Institute of Health and Care Research Policy Research Programme to conduct syntheses of evidence to inform policy development and evaluation across the full policy remit of the DHSC. The views expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the DHSC.

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